

rated resistant, with means of 8-13% SS; Leuang 152 was highly resistant (no SS).

The correlation of incidence with yield was negatively linear except for CR1014. In 10 varieties, the regression coefficient was significant or highly significant (see table).

Yield loss ranged from -0.06% in

CR1014 to 1.1% in CR58-MRI538. Based on yield losses, susceptible entries could be tentatively classified for tolerance as follows:

Highly tolerant : CR1014,
(0-0.30%) Jagannath
Moderately tolerant : Sona, Padma
(0.31-0.60%)

Least tolerant : GEB24, Pankaj,
(0.61%–higher) CR94-MRI559,
Vijaya, Jaya,
CR58-MR1538,
Bala

As yield loss varied widely among varieties, economic injury and threshold levels also varied. □

Stem borers (SB) in dryland and wetland rice

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We compared SB infestation in an

irrigated wetland field planted to *indica* varieties and in a dryland field planted to *japonica* varieties. The experimental fields were planted the same day.

At 2 wk before harvest, 150 tillers/variety were dissected. SB infestation was higher in the japonica varieties (see figure). SB species found in

wetland indicas and dryland japonicas also differed.

Five SB sp. were collected in both rice environments: *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker), *C. auricilius* Dudgeon, *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker), *Maliarpha* sp., and *Sesamia inferens* (Walker). Species abundance in the indicas was *S. incertulas* > *C. auricilius* > *C. suppressalis* > *S. inferens* > *Maliarpha* sp. In the japonicas, it was *C. suppressalis* > *C. auricilius* > *S. inferens* > *Maliarpha* sp. > *S. incertulas*.

The indicas had fewer whiteheads (1-4%) and SB (4-12 larvae) than the japonicas (1-12% whiteheads and 0-130 SB larvae). Four Brazilian japonica varieties — Japones, Maranhao Vermelho, Manteiga, and Poupa Preguica — had the highest infestation. □

Species composition (%)

Stem borer larvae (no./150 tillers)

Whiteheads (%)

Relative abundance of rice SB in *japonica* varieties planted in dryland fields and *indica* varieties planted in wetland fields. IRRI farm, 1985 wet season.

Screening of rice accessions against leaffolder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*

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We screened 32 rice accessions from the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project for resistance to LF during 1986 wet season, using a seedling screening technique.

Pregerminated seeds of accessions were sown 6 cm apart in 6 rows in 50- × 40- × 10-cm wooden seedboxes. Each accession was planted across the width of the seedbox to maintain at least 5 hills (3 plants/hill)/row. One row of susceptible check TN1 and one row of resistant check Ptb 33 were sown at

random in the seedboxes. At 7 d after seeding, the seedboxes were transferred to iron trays (60 × 40 × 15 cm) filled with 5 cm water. At 20 d after seeding, the plants in the boxes were covered with nylon net cages into which LF moths collected in the field were released at 20 moths/cage (1 male to 1 female). A cotton swab soaked in 1% sugar solution was hung inside the cage as food for the moths. Moths were allowed to oviposit for 3-4 d. At 15 d after release of moths, LF damage was assessed as percent damaged leaves in each row and accessions were rated according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

The same accessions were screened in the field at the Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU.

Reaction of rice accessions to LF. Coimbatore, India.

Accession	Cross	Damage rating ^a	
		Greenhouse	Field
BKNBR1088-83	IR2030-203-3-1/RD 1	3	3
RP1579-43	Phalguna/ARC6650	3	3
RP2199-41-25-30-55	Phalguna/TKM6	3	3
RP2199-249-209	Phalguna/TKM6	3	3
F'TB12 (donor)	—	3	3
RP2035-48-54-6	Phalguna/IR50	3	3
RP2235-85-62-8	Phalguna/IR50	3	3
RP2235-115-75-40	Phalguna/IR50	3	3
RP2235-136-65-10	Phalguna/IR50	3	3
TNAULFR83 1324	Bhavani/IR4707-106-3-2	3	3
TNAULFR832042	Bhavani/ARC10550	3	3
T2005 (donor)	—	3	3
TNI (susceptible check)	—	9	9
PTB33 (resistant check)	—	3	3

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Twelve accessions were identified as resistant in the greenhouse and in the field (see table).□

Screening rice varieties for resistance to mealybug

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We evaluated 17 varieties for resistance to mealybug *Brevinnia rehi* Lindinger. Experimental plots were 4 × 2 m with 2 seedlings/hill at 15- × 10-cm spacing

Mealybug infestation on 17 rice varieties.^a Coimbatore, India.

Variety	Infested plants (%)	Mealybugs (no./tiller)
PY 3	31.2 (33.1) a-d	43.4 (19.7) b
CO 37	23.4 (28.6) a-c	43.1 (19.6) b
CO 41	36.8 (36.7) b-e	41.7 (19.2) b
ADT31	31.9 (35.9) a-e	58.6 (23.0) c
ADT36	28.2 (31.9) a-d	61.0 (23.2) c
IR20	29.2 (42.4) c-e	64.2 (24.0) c
IR50	31.5 (34.0) a-d	92.7 (28.9) de
ACM9	45.7 (42.5) c-e	101.2 (30.1) d-f
ACM10	51.0 (45.6) de	107.6 (31.0) f
IET8616	19.1 (25.7) a	32.7 (17.1) a
AS20665	19.8 (26.3) ab	39.6 (18.9) b
AS24956	48.4 (44.0) c-e	92.0 (28.7) d
AS28838	55.0 (47.9) de	102.2 (30.2) ef
AD85001	58.0 (49.7) e	96.7 (29.5) de
AD85003	53.1 (46.8) de	101.1 (30.2) ef
TNAU831146	43.7 (41.2) c-e	98.6 (29.7) d-f
TNAU831175	52.7 (46.6) de	101.7 (30.1) d-f

^aMeans of 3 replications. Figures in parentheses are arc sine transformed values. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

with 3 replications. Twenty hills were selected for each entry and the number of mealybugs/ tiller and percentage infested plants on 20 hills/entry were recorded at 15-d intervals beginning 15 d after transplanting.

Mealybug infestation ranged from

19% to 58% (see table). IET8616 had the fewest infested plants; AD85001 was highly susceptible. ACM10 had the highest number of mealybugs/ tiller. Mealybugs/ tiller and percentage infestation were positively correlated ($r = 0.9786$).□

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DROUGHT TOLERANCE

Evaluation of drought-resistant upland rice accessions

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We evaluated 53 early-maturing rice accessions against local checks Oct 1986-Feb 1987. Seeds were sown directly in 1-m² plots at 20 cm between rows and

10 cm within rows.

Rainfall during the cropping period was 474.4 mm in 20 rainy days, with a 16-d drought spell during the vegetative phase. Drought tolerance and recovery percentage were scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Two drought-resistant varieties were identified: IRAT 170 and IR21018-97-1 (see table).□

Performance of promising upland rice varieties under moisture stress. Paramakudi, India.

Variety	cross	Drought tolerance	Drought recovery
IRAT 170	IRAT13/Palawan	3	3
IR21018-97-1	BG34-8/RP825-70-7-1//IR36	3	3
Nootripathu (local check)	—	3	5
PMK1 (improved check)	Co 25/ADT31	3	3